

Electronic Nose technology to measure soil microbial activity and classify soil metabolic status

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NATURAL EMISSIONS FROM SOIL TO ATMOSPHERE

GAS	VOCs
CO ₂	Alcohols
CH ₄	Aldehydes
NO _x	Aromatic compounds
N ₂	Esters
NH ₃	Ethers
	Hydrocarbons
	Ketones
	Terpenes
	Nitriles
	Sulfides

What is an *Electronic Nose (EN)*?

It's a sensing device mimicking the olfactory system of mammals

Features:

1. It consists of a sensor *array* capable of perceiving volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and gases present in atmosphere and heaspce of samples (the *odour*).
2. The sensing capacity of *ENs* derives from: 1) changes in the properties of sensors in the array or in their sensitive coating films induced by chemical, physical and phisico-chemical interactions with analytes; 2) transduction of such variations into electric signals; 3) data ~~processing~~ of these electric signals altogether to supply an *olfactory fingerprint*, which is specific for the analysed sample.
3. Typically, sensors in *ENs* are commonly unspecific for single analytes, but they are selective for classes of chemicals (*cross-reactivity*).

RESULTS-1

Microbial measurements

EN measurements

RESULTS-2

Microbial and EN measurements

RESULTS-3

